

Enabling Participatory Flood Monitoring Through Cloud Services

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WATERPROOFING DATA

JOINTLY FUNDED BY

Economic
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Research Council

Petrópolis: Deadly landslides wreak havoc in Brazilian city

17 February

As search and rescue teams continue to look for survivors.

Deluge of rainfall causes a landslide and flooding in Petrópolis, Brazil

More than 100 people have died in landslides and flash flooding in the Brazilian city of Petrópolis, officials say.

260 mm / 6h

269 landslides

35 - 50 houses affected

Au Brésil, les inondations de Petrópolis font une centaine de morts

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Nacional

Desastre provocado pelas fortes chuvas deixa 104 mortos em Petrópolis (RJ)

Pelo menos 269 deslizamentos foram registrados; autoridades ainda contabilizam estragos na cidade

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Noticias > Latinoamérica y el Caribe

Inundaciones en Acre, Brasil afectan a más de 130.000 personas

Al menos 10 ciudades del estado brasileño de Acre han sido afectadas por las inundaciones. | Foto: @alokoficial

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www.ubdc.ac.uk

70 mm / 24h
River 13.5m high

En el estado de Acre, norte de #Brasil, 130 mil personas de 10 ciudades fueron afectadas por las inundaciones. El gobernador decretó situación de emergencia. En las redes se movilizan con la hashtag #SOSAcre

Marcos Vicentti/Secom

De A a Z @andrezilio

#SOSenaMadureira #SOSAcre

Fotos: @MarcosVicentti

Our Aim

To design and develop *software* components to ***ingest, store and publish flood-related data*** produced by citizens and authorities. They are build upon cloud services to manage, clean, transform and integrate multiple sources of data to **help reducing the impact of flooding** in Sao Paulo and Acre in Brazil

Reduced development and replication ***effort*** for citizen science platforms and the ***simplified management*** of the infrastructure involved can help to engage communities with citizen ***participation*** and ***data production***.

Citizen Science & Cloud computing

Related Work

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Citizen Science

Participation of people from outside professional organisations in data collection and analysis as a scientific practice (Bonney et al., 2009; Phillips et al., 2021) and for disaster risk management

(Marchezini et al., 2018).

- Hazardous phenomena, early warning, and communities at risk taking actions to improve their resilience (Hicks et al., 2019).
- Local flood hazards lacking measurements of past events (Sy et al., 2020).
- “Floodings” a privileged citizen science topic (Chari et al., 2019; Marchezini et al., 2018).

Cloud Computing

Computing resources as services are useful for data management, storage and processing and computer sciences (Kobusińska et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2017).

- Data integration and automated development and operation DevOps have expanded to fields within academia (Munappy et al., 2020).
- Current IT architectures and data-driven apps might take cloud services for granted. However, citizen science hasn't (Sturm et al., 2018).
- Data pipelines (Roman et al., 2021), integration (Dong and Rekatsinas, 2018), DevOps & DataOps (Munappy et al., 2020), can support management in community-led strategies
- Communities can make more sense of data (Phillips et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2020).

*Citizen-generated high-resolution data can complement official flood-related records (Sy et al., 2020)
... and cloud services provide a good technological support*

Participatory design for data flows

Data & Methods

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Researchers and citizens collectively discuss and problematise citizens' reality to promote learning and develop critical awareness following the principles of *critical pedagogy* *for citizen science* activities

(Porto de Albuquerque and Albino de Almeida, 2020)

Participatory Design Process

Data & Methods

Worldviews
Perceptions
Understanding
Demands

Photo From: <http://k1z.blog.uni-heidelberg.de/2019/07/17/waterproofing-data-pilot-study-in-brazil>

- I. App requirements
- II. Existence (or lack) of flood-related data
- III. Enhance data production and circulation
- IV. Pathway for transformations (resilience and sustainability)

(Porto de Albuquerque et al., 2021).

Focus Groups

Data & Methods

Rain
Event

Flooding
Event

Flood
Memory

Flood
Perception Map

Self-made
rainfall gauge

Rainfall
measure

*Rainfall
Records*

*Flooding
areas*

*Weather
Forecast (*)*

Data Flows

Clients

<< HTTPS >>

Authoritative Sources

Cloud Backend

Interface components

Storage components

Pipelines Mobile & Web

Results

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Off-the-Shelf / serverless

Ingest

Query

Customised / web server

Intelligent
Pipelines

Results

Mobile

Interfaces

Web

Interfaces

Main

Discussion & Conclusions

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Key discussion elements

- Worth involving community members across the agile development
- The cloud served to speed up implementation of data pipelines
- So far hybrid (data lake + data base) but 100% cloud is the goal
- Light interfaces increase accessibility for vulnerable communities

Search for location Eg: São Paulo

- Layer
- Water level on street citizen i
- Water level in home citizen i
- Mass Movement official i
- Riverflood citizen i
- Pluviometer citizen i
- Floodzones citizen i
- Rain citizen i
- Pluviometers official i
- Floodzones official i

Map Details

WaterLevel

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- No Answer

1 2 3 4 5 6

Citizen-generated & official

Take away messages Call to action

- The communities provided material for scientists and technicians to better design solutions
- Data flows, as water and knowledge, served to engage communities and give them a voice

- Would you benefit from a community perspective?

Let's talk ...

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